

Other complexes have subnormal μ_{eff} values (1.4 to 1.5 B.M.) suggesting Cu—Cu interaction⁹. This is due to the extent of bonding; the bonding being strongest when there is no unpaired electron, *i.e.* when the magnetic moment is zero. If it is 1.73 B.M., there is no interaction of Cu—Cu bonding. The intermediate values of 1.4–1.5 in the case of 1–3 complexes suggest the mixing up of the electrons.

The powder pattern studies show that all the complexes are amorphous.

References

1. K. A. R. MITCHELL, *Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **69**, 166.
2. T. SUBRAHMANYAN, Ph.D. Thesis, I. I. T., Madras, 1981, p. 164.
3. J. S. THOMPSON, J. L. ZITZMANN, T. J. MARKS and J. A. IBERS, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1980, **5**, 146.
4. I. SOVAGO, B. HARMAN and A. GERGELY, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1980, **6**, 46.
5. D. M. ADAMS, "Metal Ligand and Related Vibrations", Edward Arnold, London, 1967, pp. 260, 282, and 310.
6. G. NARIN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 2441.
7. P. B. BAUMAN and L. B. ROGERS, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 2215.
8. R. J. DOEDENS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **21**, 209.

Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Dioxouranium(II) Complexes of Thiophene-2-aldehyde-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone

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THIOSEMICARBAZIDES and their metal complexes are well known for their pharmacological importance^{1–6}. Extensive studies on 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide derivative metal ion complexes have been reported^{7–9}. The present paper describes the synthesis and characterisation of thiophene-2-aldehyde-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone (TAPTSC) and its metal complexes with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and UO^{II}.

Experimental

Synthesis of TAPTSC: 4-Phenylthiosemicarbazide (Fluka) (8.35 g) dissolved in ethanol (50 cm³) was gradually added to thiophene-2-aldehyde (Fluka) (4.6 cm³) mixed in ethanol (30 cm³). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 2 h. A white crystalline solid separated on cooling, was filtered, washed successively with ethanol and ether, and dried over calcium chloride under reduced pressure. TAPTSC (85%), thus obtained, was insoluble in hot water but soluble in hot ethanol.

Synthesis of metal complexes of TAPTSC: To the aqueous ethanolic solution (0.004 mol) of metal acetates (AnalaR) TAPTSC (0.008 mol) dissolved in hot ethanol (60 cm³) was gradually added with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for ~1 h and left overnight. Coloured solids separated were filtered, washed successively with ethanol and ether and dried in air. The metal complexes of TAPTSC (80%) were air-stable, coloured solids and insoluble in hot water but soluble in hot ethanol. The purity of the TAPTSC and its complexes was checked by tlc, m.p./decomp. temp. and also microanalysis.

Infrared spectra (KBr) was recorded on a Beckman—Aculab 10 spectrophotometer in the range 4 000–400 cm⁻¹. Diffuse reflectance spectra were obtained in the range 200–1 000 nm on a Carl—Zeiss VSU-22 spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibility was measured at ~303 K by Gouy's method. T.G. data were recorded by heating the complexes in air upto 800° at the rate of 10° min⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) correspond to 1 : 2 metal—ligand stoichiometry. μ_{eff} value of 4.46 B.M. of the paramagnetic Co^{II} complex corresponds to three unpaired electrons and lies within the range reported for tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes^{10–12}. The diffuse reflectance spectra of Co^{II}-TAPTSC exhibit two bands, the one intense band at 17 094 cm⁻¹ and the other weak band at 19 203 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions ⁴A_{2g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) and ⁴A_{2g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) confirming spin-free tetrahedral geometry around the Co^{II} ion^{11–13}.

The Ni^{II} complex is diamagnetic indicating the formation of a spin paired, square-planar geometry around Ni^{II} in the complex^{14–16}, as was evident from one intense broad band at 24 390 cm⁻¹ in the diffuse reflectance spectra and could be assigned to transitions ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_g. The Cu^{II} complex is paramagnetic (μ_{eff} = 1.94 B.M.) for one unpaired electron¹⁷. The diffuse reflectance spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex shows one broad band at 23 255 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transition ²B_{1g} → ²E_g arising from a square-planar geometry^{16–18}. Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and UO^{II} complexes with TAPTSC are all diamagnetic.

The ir spectra of TAPTSC shows characteristic^{19–24} bands at 1 550 (N—C—N), 1 430 (C=S) and 1 310 cm⁻¹ (NH—C=S) arising from the thione form of the ligand (I) in the solid state. This is further supported by the presence of a C=S band at 810 cm⁻¹.

(I)

TABLE I—COLOUR AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF TAPTSC AND ITS COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Complete decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % Found/(Calcd.)			
				Metal	O	H	N
C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂	White	188*	—	—	55.90 (55.17)	4.24 (4.21)	16.02 (16.09)
Co(C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂) ₂	Brown	280	640	10.10 (10.17)	50.12 (49.74)	8.98 (8.45)	14.25 (14.50)
Ni(C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂) ₂	Black	280	780	10.12 (10.14)	49.50 (49.76)	8.42 (8.45)	14.28 (14.89)
Cu(C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂) ₂	Brown	240	720	10.78 (10.88)	49.52 (49.35)	8.88 (8.42)	14.88 (14.51)
Zn(C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂) ₂	Yellow	260	720	10.98 (11.18)	49.82 (49.19)	8.42 (8.41)	14.26 (14.84)
Gd(C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂) ₂	Yellow	240	690	17.62 (17.77)	45.88 (45.54)	8.28 (8.16)	18.12 (18.28)
UO ₂ (C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂) ₂	Muddy	280	—	84.10 (84.17)	86.82 (86.45)	2.64 (2.58)	10.54 (10.69)

*M.p.

(II)

In the infrared spectra of the metal complexes, bands due to N—C—N, C—S and NH—C—S disappear and new bands for azine (C=N—N=C)^{8,13,26-28} and C—S appear at 1590–1580 and 720–715 cm⁻¹, respectively, indicating coordination of metal ion through azine nitrogen and thiol sulphur of the thiol form (II) of TAPTSC. The C=N stretching frequency of the ligand observed at 1645 cm⁻¹ shifts to 1625–1615 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. The negative shift of 30–20 cm⁻¹ in ν_{C=N} of TAPTSC on complexation indicates the involvement of azomethine nitrogen^{8,11,13,14,28} with metal ions. The complexes exhibit N—N stretching bands at 1060–1050 cm⁻¹ while TAPTSC shows the same at 1030 cm⁻¹. Such positive shift of the ν_{N—N} band on complexation also indicates the bonding of the metal ions with the azomethine nitrogen atom of the ligand^{7,8,13,14}. New bands at 465–455 and 300–290 cm⁻¹ are observed in the spectra of the metal complexes due to M—N^{8,9} and M—S^{7,8,9} stretching vibrations, respectively.

Thermogravimetric studies reveal that the TAPTSC complexes do not have associated water. The complexes are thermally stable; they decompose only at relatively high temperatures (> 240°) and the decomposition being complete at temperature > 680°. The order of the thermal stability of the complexes is UO₂^{II} ~ Co^{II} ~ Ni^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cu^{II} ~ Cd^{II}.

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References

1 D. J. BAUER, L. VINCENT, C. H. KEMPE and A. W. DOWNER, *Lancet*, 1968, 2, 494.

2. V. K. PANDEY and A. K. AGGARWAL, *Acta Chenc. Indica Chem.*, 1960, 6, 166.
 3. U. SRIVASTAVA, R. B. PATHAK and S. C. BAHUL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 822.
 4. G. DOGMAGK, R. BRENNISCH and H. SCHMIDT, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1946, 33, 815.
 5. H. G. PETERING, H. H. BUSKIRK and U. E. UNDERWOOD, *Cancer Res.*, 1964, 4, 367.
 6. O. W. JOHNSON, J. W. JOYNER and R. P. PERRY, *Antibio. Chemother.*, 1952, 2, 686.
 7. M. M. MOSTAFA, A. M. SHALLAZY and A. A. EL-ASMY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, 43, 2992.
 8. P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. BEY, *Polym. Bull.*, 1979, 1, 631.
 9. P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 275.
 10. F. A. COTTON and M. GOODGAME, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 260.
 11. C. B. MAHTO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 481.
 12. N. DUNSKI and T. H. CRAWFORD, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, 35, 2707.
 13. C. B. MAHTO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 986.
 14. V. J. BABAR, D. V. KHANSNIS and V. M. SHINDE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 970.
 15. E. BANNISTER and F. A. COTTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 2276.
 16. T. S. PIPES and R. L. BELFORD, *Mol. Phys.*, 1962, 5, 169.
 17. C. DIJKGRAAF, *Chem. Acta*, 1965, 3, 88.
 18. J. FERGUSON, *Theor. Chem. Acta*, 1965, 3, 287.
 19. N. SAHA and N. C. GAYRN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14, 878.
 20. R. C. STAUFER and D. H. BUSCH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 849.
 21. K. BURGER, I. RUFFY and F. RUFFY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, 32, 2803.
 22. C. N. R. RAO and R. VANKATARAGHWAN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1956, 34, 1756.
 23. P. W. SADLER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 957.
 24. E. LIEBER, C. N. R. RAO, C. N. PILLAI, J. RAMACHANDRAN and H. D. HITES, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1958, 36, 801.
 25. K. MUKKANTI, K. B. PANDEYA and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 641.
 26. M. S. PATIL and J. R. SAHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 944.
 27. A. SYAMAL and K. S. KALE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16, 46.
 28. P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 418.
 29. M. A. ALI and A. BOSR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, 39, 265.
 30. B. DASH and S. K. MAHAPATRA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, 37, 271.